

WUYISHAN NATIONAL PARK: A THREATENED BIODIVERSITY HOTSPOT BY GLOBAL WARMING

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1. Abstract

Wuyishan National Park is one of the first five national parks in China's mainland. It is the only National Park in China recognized as both a World Biosphere Reserve and a World Cultural and Natural Heritage Site by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization. The unique geographical environment contributes to the best-preserved primary forest ecosystem in the subtropics. The Wuyi Mountains within the Park are justifiably valued in southeastern China for studies of plants, birds, insects, amphibians, and reptiles. Since 2010, 18 new species (never before discovered) have been discovered and 5 new record species to China have been found in the Park. However, biodiversity in the Wuyi Mountains is not only being affected, but possibly threatened by climate change. Climate warming is not only changing ecosystem hydrothermal dynamics but is also affecting the growth, distribution, and reproduction of organisms, altering ecosystem species composition and biodiversity. Therefore, it is of great theoretical and practical significance to monitor and study the long-term biodiversity changes in Wuyishan National Park to aid in biodiversity conservation and protect the ecosystems under future climate change.

2. Keywords

Wuyishan National Park; Biodiversity; Mountains; Climate change; Warming; Conservation

Wuyishan National Park (27°31'20" ~ 27°55'49" N, 117°24'13" ~ 117°59'19" E, Figure 1) is one of the first five national parks in China's mainland. Located in southeastern China, in northwest Fujian and extending northwards into Jiangxi, it was established by the State Council of the People's Republic on September 30, 2021 (Central People's Government of the P.R.C. 2021). It is

the only National Park in China recognized as both a World Biosphere Reserve and a World Cultural and Natural Heritage Site by the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO 1999). Wuyishan National Park spans an area of 1280 km², with an average elevation of 1200 m ranging between 300 and 2158 m above sea level. The elevational gradient and unique geographical environment contribute to the best-preserved primary forest ecosystem in the subtropics and a gene bank of rare and endemic plants (He et al. 2018).

Figure 1: A vista of Wuyishan National Park showing local flora and elevational range.

Wuyishan National Park is known as a biodiversity hotspot of global significance. Field surveys conducted over decades have recorded 2799 species (including subspecies and varieties) of higher plants in 269 families, 239 species (191 genera) of algae in 73 families, 503 species (83 genera) of fungi in 38 families and 558 species (332 genera) of wild vertebrates in 5 classes, 35 orders, 125 families. There are 6849 species of insects in 599 families and 31 orders, 139 species of higher aquatic plants in 51 genera and 42 families, 67 species of zooplankton, and 104 species of fish in 56 genera and 22 families (Wuyishan National Park 2017). The Wuyi Mountains within the Park are justifiably valued in southeastern China for studies of plants, birds, insects, amphibians, and reptiles. Since 2010, 18 new species (never before discovered) have been discovered in Wuyishan National Park, including *Odorrana huanggangensis* (Chen et al. 2010), *Thymaris ruficollaris*, *Thymaris sulcatus* (Sheng & Sun 2011), *Eudonia abrupta* (Li 2012), *Gamasholaspis aliventroanalis*, *Lattinela robustocalcaris* (Ma & Lin 2011), *Gastrodia fujianensis* (Liang et al. 2019), *Sinoennea pupoidea* (Zhou et al. 2011), *Parasteatoda wangi* (Jin & Zhang 2013), *Rhizomyia leptodicrata*, *Rhizomyia meniscata* (Jiao & Bu 2013), *Megophrys ombrophila* (Messenger et al. 2019), *Pseudostellaria wuyishanensis* (Luo et al. 2021), *Impatiens wuyiensis* (Wang et al. 2020), *Neottia wuyishanensis* (Chen et al. 2021), *Rana wuyiensis* (Wu et al. 2021), *Typhrasa polycystis* (Wang et al. 2021), *Drupeus guadunensis* (Hájek 2021). In addition, 5 new record species to China have been found in the Park, including *Vellonifer doncasteri* (Fang et al.

2010), *Rubus parvifolius* (An et al. 2019), *Hypsibius pedrottii Bertolani* (Fan & Sun 2014), *Palaina pusilla*, *Carychium noduliferum* (Zhou et al. 2011).

The Wuyi Mountains, located in subtropical areas, are especially suitable for many specialist species, due to the elevation gradient as well as the rugged terrain that facilitates the survival of endemic species (Myres 1990; Menendez-Guerrero et al. 2020). In addition, biodiversity in Wuyishan National Park has been well protected from local human effects. However, local weather records show that global human effects may be more important with a large increase in annual temperature since 1957 (Figure 2). For example, warming at the Park has increased homogenization of vegetation activity (~35 %) along the elevation gradient during 1998-2018, leading to altered vegetation structure and land cover that constitute bird habitats (Li et al. 2021; Bellard et al. 2012). Birds are sensitive to environmental changes and the bird community structure has changed in an uneven manner sequentially at Wuyishan (Xu et al. 2021). Climate warming is changing ecosystem hydrothermal dynamics as well as affecting the growth, distribution, and reproduction of organisms, altering ecosystem species composition and biodiversity (Maina et al. 2022; Riddell et al. 2021; Li et al. 2021).

Biodiversity in the Wuyi Mountains is not only being affected, but possibly threatened by climate change (Xu et al. 2021). Among the numerous wild animals with historical distribution records in Wuyishan National Park, some species have not been recorded in the wild for many years (Xu 2022). More attentions should be paid not only to the discovery of new species but undoubtedly also to the loss of known species. Biodiversity loss will inevitably affect ecosystem structure, stability, function and resilience by pushing many species toward extinction (Chase et al. 2020). Different from previous assumptions (Riddell et al. 2021; Burrows et al. 2011; Loarie et al. 2009; Warren et al. 2018; Trisos et al. 2020), the vulnerability of all taxa at a site exposure to climate change may be not equal (Riddell et al. 2021). Estimates from climate projections are unlikely to accurately reflect the local conditions without accounting for the effects of microhabitat buffering on climate change. Therefore, it is of great theoretical and practical significance to monitor and study the long-term biodiversity changes in Wuyishan National Park to aide in biodiversity conservation and protect the ecosystems under future climate change.

Figure 2: Mean annual temperature from 1957 to 2021. Data obtained from <https://rp5.ru/>.

Declarations

Conflict of interests: The authors declare no conflict of interests.

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Availability of data and materials

Mean annual temperature data are available at <https://rp5.ru/>.

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References

1. An C, Chen M, Zhuang YX, Meng J, Yang CZ (2019) New distribution records of angiosperm in Fujian (VI). *Subtropical Plant Sci* 48(3): 291-294.
2. Bellard C, Bertelsmeier C, Leadley P, Thuiller W, Courchamp F (2012) Impacts of climate change on the future of biodiversity. *Ecol Lett* 15(4):365-377.
3. Burrows MT, Schoeman DS, Buckley LB, Moore P, Poloczanska ES et al. (2011) The pace of shifting climate in marine and terrestrial ecosystems. *Science* 334(6056): 652-655.

4. Central People's Government of the People's Republic of China (2021) Reply of The State Council on approval of the establishment of Mount Wuyi National Park.
5. Chase JM, Blowes SA, Knight TM, Gerstner K, May F (2020) Ecosystem decay exacerbates biodiversity loss with habitat loss. *Nature* 584(7820): 238-243.
6. Chen HB, Jin XH. (2021) *Neottia wuyishanensis* (Orchidaceae: Neottieae), a new species from Fujian, China. *Plant Diversity* 43(5): 426-431.
7. Chen XH, Zhou KY, Zheng GM (2010) A new species of the genus *Sodorrana* from China (Anura, Ranidae). *Acta Zootaxonomica Sinica* 35(1): 206-211.
8. Fan RN, Sun XZ. (2014) A newly recorded species of genus *Hypsibius* (Tardigrada: Hypsibiidae) from the Wuyi Mountains, Southeastern China. *Jour of Anhui Agri Sci* 42(29):10146, 10149.
9. Fang Y, Chen LS, Wang M (2010) First record of the tortricid genus *Vellonifer* Razowski (Lepidoptera) from China. *Jour of South China Agri Univ.* 31(3): 121-122.
10. Hájek J (2021) A new species of *Drupeus* Lewis from eastern China (Coleoptera: Ptilodactylidae: Cladotominae). *Zootaxa* 4996(1): 183-188.
11. He S, Gallagher L, Su Y, Wang L, Cheng HG (2018) Identification and assessment of ecosystem services for protected area planning: A case in rural communities of Wuyishan national park pilot. *Ecosyst Serv* 31:169-180.
12. Jiao KL, Bu WJ. (2013) New records of *Rhizomyia* Kieffer (Diptera, Cecidomyiidae) in China with description of two new species. *Acta Zootaxonomica Sinica* 38(2):356-362.
13. Jin C, Zhang F (2013) A new spider species of the genus *Parasteatoda* Archer (Araneae, Theridiidae) in Wuyi Mountain, Fujian, China. *Acta Zootaxonomica Sinica* 38(3): 520-524.
14. Li WC (2012) One new species of the genus *Eudonia* Billberg (Lepidoptera: Crambidae: Scopariinae) from China. *Entomotaxonomia* 34(2): 267-269.
15. Li X, Wu PF, Guo FT, Hu XS (2021) A geographically weighted regression approach to detect divergent changes in the vegetation activity along the elevation gradients over the last 20 years. *Forest Ecol and Manag* 490: 119089.
16. Liang M, Chen XY, Liu JF, Chen SP (2019) *Gastrodia fujianensis* (Orchidaceae, Epidendroideae, Gastrodieae), a new species from China. *Phytotaxa* 391(4): 269-272.
17. Loarie SR, Duffy PB, Hamilton H, Asner GP, Field CB, Ackerly DD (2009) The velocity of climate change. *Nature* 462:1052-1055.
18. Luo X, Yang QY, Zhang Z, Zhu P, Ma L, Chen XY, Lin SY, Chen SP (2021) *Pseudostellaria wuyishanensis*, a new species of Caryophyllaceae from Fujian, China. *PhytoKeys* 181:21-28.
19. Ma LM, Lin JZ (2011) A new species of the genus *Gamasholaspis* and a new species of the genus *Lattinela* from Wuyi Mountain, Fujian Province, China (Acari: Mesostigmata: Parholaspidae). *Acta Arachnologica Sinica* 20(2):71-76.
20. Maina FZ, Kumar SV, Albergel C, Mahanam SP. (2022) Warming, increase in precipitation, and irrigation enhance greening in High Mountain Asia. *Commun Earth Environ* 3(1):43.

21. Menendez-Guerrero PA, Green DM, Davies TJ (2020) Climate change and the future restructuring of Neotropical anuran biodiversity. *Ecography* 43(2):222-235.
22. Messenger KR, Dahn HA, Liang YR, Xie P, Wang Y, Lu CH (2019) A new species of the genus *Megophrys* Gunther, 1864 (Amphibia: Anura: Megophryidae) from Mount Wuyi, China. *Zootaxa* 4554(2): 561-583.
23. Myres N (1990) The biodiversity challenge: expanded hot-spots analysis. *Environmentalist* 10 (4):243-256.
24. Riddell EA, Iknayan KJ, Hargrove L, Tremor S, Patton JL, Ramirez R, Wolf BO, Beissinger SR (2021) Exposure to climate change drives stability or collapse of desert mammal and bird communities. *Science* 371: 633-636.
25. Sheng ML, Sun SP (2011) Three new species of the genus *thymaris* Förster from Jiangxi province with a key to species known from China (Hymenoptera, Ichneumonidae, Tryphoninae). *Acta Zootaxonomica Sinica* 36:961-969.
26. Trisos CH, Merow C, Pigot AL (2020) The projected timing of abrupt ecological disruption from climate change. *Nature* 580:496-501.
27. UNESCO (1999) World Heritage Convention, "Mount Wuyi".
28. Wang JS, Lu YF, Xu YL, Jin SH, Jin XF (2020) *Impatiens wuyiensis* (Balsaminaceae), a new species from Fujian of Southeast China, based on morphological and molecular evidences. *Bot Stud* 61:29.
29. Wang SN, Hu YP, Chen JL, Qi LL, Zeng H, et al. (2021) First record of the rare genus *Typhrasa* (Psathyrellaceae, Agaricales) from China with description of two new species. *MycKeys* 79:119-128.
30. Warren R, Price J, Graham E, Forstenhaeusler N, VanDerWal J (2018) The projected effect on insects, vertebrates, and plants of limiting global warming to 1.5°C rather than 2°C. *Science* 360:791-795.
31. Wu YQ, Shi SC, ZhangHG, Chen WC, Cai B, et al. (2021) A new species of the genus *Rana* sensu lato Linnaeus, 1758 (Anura, Ranidae) from Wuyi Mountain, Fujian Province, China. *ZooKeys* 1065:101-124.
32. Wuyishan National Park (2017) Park Profile.
33. Xu XJ (2022) Biodiversity research of mammals and birds in Wuyishan National Park using infrared cameras. *Wuyi Sci Jour* 38(1):10-17.
34. Xu ZF, Ma L, Chen MW, Bai JP, Chen P, et al. (2021) The avian community structure of Wuyi Mountains is sensitive to recent climate warming. *Sci Total Environ* 776:145825.
35. Zhou WC, Lin J, Xiao Q (2011) Study on species diversity of land seashell in Wuyi Mountain nature reserve. *Jour of Fujian Forestry Sci and Tech* 38(3):1-7.